

Guidelines and Training Module for AMM Advise Ready (MS11)

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Means of Verification

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1. Overview

A central component of the Climate Farm Demo project is the completion of a GHG farm audit (to establish the GHG emissions profile for each demonstration farmer), as well as supporting the demonstration farmer to adopt suitable, farm specific adaptation and mitigation measures (AMM's), before completing a second audit to estimate progress in reducing GHG emissions. In addition, each CFD farmer is expected to host three farm demo events during the project lifetime (Year 2 – Year 7).

2. Purpose

The purpose of this document (Milestone 2.1) is to

- Provide general guidance for use by Climate Farm Advisors in the completion of the farm GHG audit and the creation of the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan (AMP), thereby
- Enabling Advisors to lead and support the increased adoption of climate smart farming practices by CFD demonstration farmers, and
- Creating opportunities for future farm demonstration events.

3. Completing the GHG farm audits

It is widely recognised that “what you measure, you manage”. Therefore, the starting point for the farmer’s journey in the project is the establishment of a GHG baseline (including both GHG emissions and carbon removals (or sequestration)). Climate Farm Advisers (CFAs) will conduct this “baseline” evaluation (or audit) between M12 (September 2023) and M18 (March 2024). CFAs can select one of the tools approved by the project (WP5, see next section). Typically the following data is required to complete a GHG farm evaluation:

- General information on the farm: name, location, type – livestock, arable crops, horticulture/perennial crops, area farmed etc.;
- Details of cropping areas and cultivated crops: production data, energy and material inputs and outputs, fertiliser (chemical and organic) purchases and usage etc.;
- Details of livestock production: herd/ flock size, annual milk/ meat production, feeding, housing type and housing periods, degree of feed self-sufficiency, manure and slurry management methods, energy consumption, water consumption, external inputs, waste production etc.

We expect to include an analysis of carbon stocks on the farm, and to utilise tools employing predictive models to estimate the amount of carbon stocks. Details regarding farm size and soil type are likely to be required. Data collection is critical to the success of the audit, as poor data leads to poor and misleading results. While the completion of one’s first GHG audit may appear daunting, CFA’s should not unduly fear the data collection process as they will be familiar with the majority of the data required (as they are currently using it for other purposes).

The cooperation and involvement of the farmer is essential to obtain real and correct data for the evaluation, and it is equally important that the CFA shares the results of the assessment with the farmer. Once the baseline is established, the next step involves comparing the farm specific figures with known benchmarks (European, national, regional or local figures), before then identifying mitigation and adaption actions already used (positives or strengths) and AMM's currently not used (gaps or weaknesses).

Before the farm audit	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Familiarise yourself with the GHG evaluation tool, and the various data required 2. Identify data sources available to you 3. Gather data from available sources (online databases, previous records relating to the farm, data already held by the farmer) 4. Begin completion of the input screens
During the farm audit	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Complete data collection 2. Verify/ validate data reliability
After the farm audit	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Record details (data, results) on project databases 2. Provide copy of evaluation to the farmer 3. Present and discuss results with the farmer, including appropriate benchmarking of the farm's GHG emissions with known measures or targets 4. Identify farm specific Adaptation and Mitigation Measures (AMM's) to be incorporated into the farming system.

Table 1: Before, during and after the GHG farm audit

Once the results of the farm audit have been shared and discussed with the PDF, the CFA should aim to agree a minimum number of priority AMM's (those which can have the greatest impact in reducing GHG emissions, are most suited to the farm, and which the farmer has agreed to implement). The selection of these measure will form the basis for the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan (AMP, see next section).

Training will be provided to CFA's in terms of this process or approach (M15, led by WP1, with training content provided by WP's 2 and 5). Finally, template documents will be provided to support CFA's in the completion of each GHG farm audit.

4. Creating the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan

The Adaptation and Mitigation Plan is a document that outlines each PDF's pathway to improve its climate-related environmental performance. The AMP results from the collaboration between the farmer and the CFA. Starting from the baseline audit results and benchmarking process, the farmer and their advisor can identify areas of action/change and choose the most appropriate actions (adaptation and mitigation measures – AMM's) to take. First of all the CFA should take into account the AMMs already adopted by the PDF and consider them a strength; on this basis other AMMs can be selected for future use. While there is no recommended number of measures for each farm, typically between three and five AMM's should be agreed. The exact number of measures included in the plan will depend on the individual farm, the farm's baseline (current GHG emissions level), the ambition of the farmer etc. The key requirement is that the measures selected have been discussed and agreed with the PDF (this will increase the likelihood of adoption). Remember also that the plan can be reviewed by the CFA and the PDF during the project's lifetime, and can be adjusted to reflect new AMM's, increased ambition of the PDF, new policy regulations etc.

It is expected that this AMP template will include sections relating to:

- Baseline farm GHG emissions (from GHG evaluation or audit);
- List of AMM's currently used on the farm/ by the farmer;
- Identification of areas for action/ change;
- List of AMM's selected for future use (limit to two or three actions at most per farm);

- Future farm GHG emissions, based on adoption of AMM's (if available); and
- Farmer commitment to action

The CFD project doesn't need a "perfect" AMP, but a "feasible" plan. While each AMP will be tailored to the specific circumstances, it is important that each plan includes objectives that challenge the farmer to change, to adapt their farming system, and to achieve results beyond their current performance. The level of challenge will depend on both the farmer and their farm. The AMP must take into account the characteristics of both the farmer and their farm. A "successful" advisor will incorporate these considerations into their discussions with the farmer.

Training and template documents will be provided to CFAs. CFA's will be expected to complete the AMP for each PDF between M13 and M36, that is from just as the GHG farm audit is completed to some months after the completion of the audit. The choice of how each CFA approaches this is left with the CFA, provided that all AMP's are created and operable by M36.

Can the GHG Farm Audit and the AMP be created at the same time?

If the advisor wishes to do this, that is acceptable. However, it may be preferable to consider initially completing the GHG Farm Audit, before sharing the results with the farmer, and allowing the farmer time to reflect on his GHG performance. Then the CFA could schedule a separate, follow-up meeting to discuss, identify and agree the farm specific AMM's and "write up" or formalise the AMP.

Farmer	Farm
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commitment to action • Needs • Mindset and attitude • Motivations • Management capacity and ability • Family circumstances • Age • Social connections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buildings, facilities and equipment • Availability of workers and their capacities • Investment capabilities • Economic and market context • External constraints e.g. policy/ regulation

Table 2: Items to consider when completing an AMP relating to both the farmer and their farm

The advisor should tailor the content of the AMP to take into account the characteristics of both the farmer and their farm.

Figure 1: Steps in completing an AMP

CFAs should monitor progress made on each farm on a regular or annual basis. This will most likely involve checking whether the agreed actions have been taken (or not), as well as investigating the reasons for non-action (where agreed actions have not been taken); and will also provide an opportunity to record any other adaptation and mitigation action(s) taken by the farmer in addition to agreed actions. There are two intermediate monitoring points identified in the project (M36 and M54). It is not a requirement to complete audits at these intermediate monitoring points, but at a minimum the AMP should be reviewed, with particular attention paid to progress made in the incorporation of the chosen AMM's into the farming system. And there is also an opportunity to select additional measures (if significant progress has been made with the measures already chosen).

A second farm GHG evaluation or audit will be completed towards the end of the project (M76, March 2028). The responsibility for implementation of the agreed actions rests with the CFD farmer, but they should be supported in this by the CFA (see Section 8). There are no penalties if the farmer does not adopt the agreed AMM's, but the project will be interested in the reasons for non-adoption (this is the sometimes referred to as the intention-action gap).

It is anticipated that an annual report to your National Coordinator will also be required.

Figure 2: Measurement, Planning, Implementation and Monitoring

5. Tool selection

An inventory of tools suitable for the assessment of farm GHG emissions is being compiled in WP5. The list should be finalised by the end of September 2023, and will be presented at the CFD Annual Meeting during October. As of June 2023, WP5 had identified 38 potential tools, of which 22 appear to meet the criteria for use by project partners in the current project. Further analysis and verification of each tool's suitability will be conducted before the final list of “approved” tools will be made available.

CFA's can select the tool which they are familiar with, or have used previously (provided that it is “approved” for use). If CFA's have not used a tool previously, they can choose a tool from all of those “approved”.

A description of each “approved” tool, plus guidelines relating to tool selection will be provided. Training will also be provided, commencing in M14.

6. List of mitigation and adaptation actions

A list of Adaptation and Mitigation Measures (AMM's) to reduce GHG emissions and increase carbon sequestration is being compiled in WP5. The list should be finalised by the end of September 2023, and will be presented at the CFD Annual Meeting during October. Relevant, farm specific AMM's should be selected for implementation by the PDF and promoted at CFD demonstration farm events.

While this project is still awaiting a final list of mitigation actions, an indication of the type of AMM's which are likely to be included can be gleaned from previous or current EU projects. For example, the ClieNFarms project (<https://clienfarms.eu/>) provides a range of farm-level solutions that can reduce climate impact of agricultural production systems in Europe (mitigation measures), while the LIFE

AgriAdapt (<https://agriadapt.eu>) project provides a range of sustainable adaptation measures to increase the resilience of EU farming systems to climate change.

ClieNFarms Catalogue of Climate Solutions: <https://cliefarms.eu/solutions/>

AgriAdapt Sustainable Adaptation Measures <https://awa.agriadapt.eu/en/adaptations/>

As of June 2023, WP5 had identified 230 potential Adaptation Measures and 53 potential Mitigation Measures from a review of previous projects. These measures will be reviewed and categorised over the next number of months before the final list of “approved” measures will be made available.

Finally, while it is the responsibility of the CFA to familiarise themselves with the complete list of AMM's (once available), it is likely that the CFA will identify the most usable AMM's for their own local/ regional context, and make most use of these with their PDF's. That said, a strength of the project will be the opportunity for knowledge exchange between partners (including CFA's), so it is important that CFA's are open to trying new solutions with PDF's.

7. Selection of farm specific mitigation and adaptation actions

Once the farm audit is completed, the CFA should have some indication of the potential AMM's which could be used on the farm. The CFA should use their local knowledge of farming systems, the particular farm and the individual farmer to identify and recommend the most appropriate actions for the specific farm. The individual farmer may have a personal interest in applying a particular technology or solution, and provided that this can have an impact in reducing GHG emissions, then the advisor should support the farmer in achieving this. Other considerations include:

- a. The potential impact of the specific AMM on both GHG emissions and the performance of the farming system – select those measures which can have the greatest impact on reducing GHG emissions, can be adopted relatively easily, and can have a positive impact on the farming system;
- b. Cost - start with AMM's that can reduce costs/ increase profits;
- c. Management skills of the farmer - some measures require increased skills;
- d. Currently available farm facilities; and
- e. Supports/ incentives available (from EU or Government, or from milk/ meat processors).

Some of the identified AMM's may not currently be available, but will become available in the coming years. An example here would be the widespread availability of methane reducing feed additives. So, the focus should always be on those AMM's that are currently available and ready for use by the farmer (while the CFA should record a farmer's interest in a particular new AMM in the future).

The CFA won't have to recommend all measures for all farms. Instead, they should focus (initially at least) on recommending those measures which are expected to have the greatest impact (in terms of climate mitigation or adaptation) with the highest likelihood of implementation. Small, quick wins can build the farmer's confidence in climate action (and the project), while also cementing the relationship between the farmer and their advisor. Over time, the farmer should be encouraged and supported to take on additional AMM's, with some of these requiring greater management skills, or more time, or a level of investment.

8. Supporting the farmer to implement their chosen actions

Having completed the farm audit, quantified the farm’s GHG emissions, identified the chosen adaptation and mitigation measures, a question arises as to how the Climate Farm Advisor (CFA) can support the farmer, as they implement the action(s). Is this even part of the ClimateFarmDemo project? Yes, it is clearly stated in the project proposal that the CFA will accompany the pilot demo farmers (PDF’s). In addition, Task 2.2 is dedicated to putting the AMP into practice.

“Climate Farm Advisors advise and support PDFs in implementing the CSF practices along the journey.”

“Close cooperation between PDFs and CFAs will ensure the implementation of farm plans.”

Research, as well as adviser experience, has identified both barriers and opportunities for EU farmers to adopt mitigation practices. In some cases, farmers are simply unaware of the practice, do not have the right mindset, is reluctant to change, or their farm is not economically viable (“you cannot be green, when you are in the red”). While these barriers will undoubtedly have to be overcome, there also exists opportunities to exploit. These include providing a farm specific measure of GHG emissions, agreeing a pathway forward, supporting the farmer to develop an interest in mitigation and adaptation actions and pointing out the economic benefits of climate action (ideally that the action either reduces costs, or increases revenues, at no additional cost to the farmer; or the availability of subsidies or incentives such as rewarding mechanisms), or any other motivation for change that the farmer is in favour of. On this last point, the synergies with the CSA project should make it possible to speed up the deployment of AMM’s.

It is likely that you will work with farmers at different stages along the innovation-decision process (Rogers, 2003) and that your role will change as you move along the continuum. You may firstly have to develop the farmer’s interest in the solution, and meet their information needs. You may then have to support the farmer as they pilot test the action/ technology, and then help them to interpret the results. Next, you could be involved in advising the farmer on steps to scale up the initial test, to a larger part (or the entire) farming system. All the time, you can provide support to the farmer allowing them to measure their performance or progress against other farmers. Some farmers will be comfortable moving at a faster speed (in terms of incorporation of the AMM into their farming system), and others will want to take a more cautious approach.

Figure 3: Rogers' Innovation Decision Process

Another way of thinking about supporting the PDF’s is in terms of the various steps along the Adoption Curve (Gomes and Reidsma, 2021). This is similar to Rogers’ model, but focuses on the steps between the five stages.

Step A: From Nothing to Investigation: The focus of this step is making farmers aware of the chosen AMM’s and will likely involve large-scale farmer events, media and farmer networks. Farmers need to have an open mindset. Ideally in this project, the PDF’s selected would have already completed this step (prior to their selection). But this is not a requirement.

Step B: From Investigation to Pilot: During this step, the advisor can play a key role in providing information about or access to the tools and supports to pilot test the new solution, allowing the farmer to overcome the practical on-farm challenges that come with implementation.

Step C: From Pilot to Initial Adoption: If the pilot is successful, the farmer is more likely to continue. However, there may be competing priorities and the advisor may have to ensure that the farmer remains focussed on the goal of reducing GHG emissions (in the face of other goals).

Step D: From Initial to Advanced Adoption: The challenge here is to demonstrate to the farmer that the sustainability of their farm will not be undermined through complete transition to the new way of farming. The advisor can assist here through financial analysis and forecasting.

From A to D: Some farmers will be comfortable moving at a fast pace along the entire curve, while others will wish to progress at a slower pace.

The model is included below (Figure 4).

Figure 4: AD Adoption Curve Framework (from Gomes and Reidsma, 2021)

How Knowledge Transfer Impact Happens at the Farm Level: Insights from Advisers and Farmers in the Irish Agricultural Sector (Cawley *et al.*, 2023)

It is likely that Climate Farm Adviser (CFA's) will make an impact through a combination of advisory activities, focussing on relevant and user-friendly content, which stimulates farmer learning and motivates their decision to apply new knowledge.

As a CFA, it is likely that you will play a dual role, firstly as a source of expertise in delivering science-based knowledge, and secondly as a facilitator to draw out tacit knowledge from farmers (either in one-to-one conversations or in a group-based activities).

The farmer must also want to engage, learn, and apply newly acquired knowledge. The main reason (or motivation) for the farmer to engage is to improve their farm performance. It is often the farm related advantages of the AMM's that motivates farmers to implement them (and not necessarily their concern for the climate).

Finally, the importance of trust is key to ensuring impact. This depends both on the reputation and familiarity of the organisation and of the trust between the adviser and the farmer (which builds over time). Trust between farmers enhances peer-to-peer learning.

Each project partner has their own way of interacting with farmers. There is no recommended way of supporting farmers in this project, nor indeed a set number of visits that each PDF should receive (see also section 12 regarding the project budget). However, it is important that the PDF is supported in the implementation of their AMP. There is an amount included for national travel in each partner's travel budget, but it is not calculated based on a specified number of visits to the farm. Rather it is a contribution towards the cost of supporting the farmer. Remember also that the PDF's can be supported in other ways, including phone calls, emails, text messages, membership of a WhatsApp group, invitations to project activities, benchmarking etc. One method which harnesses the power of farmer-to-farmer learning is the creation of a PDF farmer group, with meetings scheduled on members' farms on a regular (perhaps quarterly) basis. In this way individual PDF's can be supported by one another while also building commitment to the project and the adoption of AMM's.

Finally, listed below are the ClimateFarmDemo Top Tips for Supporting Your CFD Demo Farmer.

1. **Get to know the farmers you are trying to influence.** A range of factors, such as age, access to finance and attitude towards risk, impact the willingness of farmers to change their farming practices.
2. **Highlight the positives** including good practices and the progress made without being afraid of calling out the areas for improvement.
3. **Keep it simple.** Farmers need to know that the recommended solutions are backed up by science i.e. that they work to reduce GHG emissions...but don't necessarily need to know all of the details.
4. Always **prepare before meeting with the farmer.** Review the farm audit and the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan (AMP), make a list of all of the items you want to cover.
5. **Provide ongoing support** through (short) visits, phone consultations, membership of a WhatsApp group, emails, invitations to events etc.
6. **Consider organising all of your CFD demo farmers into a group** (or working with colleagues to jointly form such a group), and organise some group-based activities. For example, an annual workshop to discuss and review actions taken.
7. **Prepare for a long time horizon:** it may be a number of years before there are measureable environmental and economic outcomes. Also, tackle the adoption of one or two mitigation practices at a time...avoid identifying a list of actions to be taken. There is a better chance of success by focusing on a short list of tasks...there is always the next time.
8. **Familiarise yourself with currently available rewards and incentives,** available from Government/ EU or from the marketplace. Be able to highlight what is required of the farmer to avail of these.
9. Consider what else you can do to **create an enabling environment** that facilitates the farmer taking climate action.
10. **Take an interest.** Don't forget the personal touch – make the connection with the farmer, and their family. And most importantly, listen to the farmer's arguments, fears and wishes.

9. Monitoring progress

While the second GHG farm audit will be the ultimate measure of progress (change in GHG emissions between initial and final audit), other ways of monitoring progress by the PDF exist. These are suggestions, and are not in all cases a requirement of the project.

1. Further audits can be completed voluntarily on an annual basis – this may be an option for some advisors/ farmers.
2. Progress on the implementation of agreed actions can be monitored (without completing an audit). This could take the form of an annual review of the AMP, with the level of progress made recorded against the agreed action. The reason (barrier) for non-adoption should also be recorded. The focus here is on the adoption of the agreed AMM's (with the expectation that AMM adoption will lead to a reduction in GHG's). As the AMP is expected to be dynamic, this annual review could

also reset the objectives for the year ahead, and include specific steps to overcome barriers encountered.

3. Ongoing contact / conversations/ correspondence between the CFA and PDF can provide insights regarding the adoption of the AMM. The CFA should be prepared to enquire about the implementation of the AMM and “nudge” the PDF in the right direction.
4. Finally, benchmarking of PDF performance can be a useful way of identifying those farmers making significant progress in the adoption of AMM's (and those that are not). In that way, a targeted approach can be taken to working with those farmers that appear to need more advisory support.

10. Using the results of the farm audit at Climate Farm Demo events

CFD demonstration events are a central component of the overall project. They will allow CFD advisers, working with the PDF, and other relevant AKIS actors, to demonstrate and promote climate solutions to a wider farming audience. These events will provide an opportunity for the PDF (who has used the AMM on their farm) to share their experiences and insights, while supporting knowledge exchange and co-creation among farmers and other actors. It is expected that CFD demonstration events will:

- Allow climate solutions/ AMM's be demonstrated in situ;
- Provide an opportunity for the PDF to share their experiences;
- Leverage the advisory and support efforts with the PDF by reaching more farmers;
- Build trust between CFD Advisers, AKIS actors and farmers; and
- Highlight the initial starting point (first event) and progress made on the farm over time (at second and subsequent events);
 - First demo event – present the starting point or baseline, explain how the figures were arrived at, share the AMP for the farm;
 - Second demo event – review progress made, focussing on good practices continued and new mitigation practices adopted, demonstrate a specific AMM adopted;
 - Third demo event – again review progress made, present the results of the second audit, compare results with those from the first audit, highlight emissions reduction achieved and explain how the various on-farm changes contributed to the emissions reduction over time.

Where possible identify the AMM's used on the farm, and provide the impacts of these practices on GHG emissions (and ammonia emissions and C sequestration, if relevant). These impacts should be available from the tool used for the audit. Other environmental considerations (biodiversity, water quality) should also be highlighted. And ideally, if possible, the impact of the AMM's on farm system profitability and sustainability would also be highlighted.

You may also consider sharing the relevant information in a written form (a handout) to complement the physical demonstration and discussion. Such a document may also contain background information (farm details etc.), details of how the solutions work and advantages and disadvantages of the solutions used.

Please remember to include the ClimateFarmDemo logo and funding acknowledgement on any printed material, display boards etc., generated for the CFD demonstration event. The ClimateFarmDemo logo and funding acknowledgement can be found on the CFD SharePoint.

11. Budget considerations

A question which is asked relates to the cost of implementing the chosen AMM's on the farm. Firstly, there is no budget to pay for measures. Secondly, a significant number of the measures are likely to be cost neutral or even lead to reduced costs for the farmer. The CFA should initially focus on those measures which can benefit the farmer financially once implemented. For other measures involving a cost, the farmer may still be willing to implement them, if there is either a longer-term benefit, or some other non-financial benefit (e.g. reduced workload, better working environment). Finally, there may in some cases be a financial incentive available (separate to the project budget) to support with the adoption of specific AMM's. This could be a supplier payment or incentive (from a milk/ meat processor, for example), or a

Regarding the funding available to accompanying and supporting the PDF over the duration of the project, 15 days are allocated per farm (over six years, or 2.5 days per year). This will have been included in each partner's budget, with reference to the number of PDF's to be supported by each partner.

Training related to the AMP, supporting the PDF, monitoring progress in reducing GHG emissions etc. will be provided at the annual meetings or through online events (organised by WP2 or thematic leaders). An overall budget allocation for training has been included under WP1 for each partner. Each partner will benefit from approximately three days training and capacity building activities on AMP during the project.

12. Further information

Further guidelines will be developed relating to the adaptation and mitigation measures (AMM's), the recommended tools/ calculators for estimating GHG emissions and removals, and the delivery of demonstration events. These guidelines will provide more details and resources relating to specific project tasks.

Deliverables & Milestones		Delivered at
D2.2	Manual for the application of AMPs on farm Section regarding (i) AMP format and (ii) guidelines for AMP implementation	M24 M12 (Sept. 2023)
D3.1	Protocol for Climate Smart Farming demonstration activities and campaigns	M9
D5.1	Digital repository for carbon and environmental models, methods and tools	M18
D5.2	Farm GHG accounting methodology and guidelines First version GHG accounting guideline	M24 M12 (Sept. 2023)
M2.3	Referential for data collection ready	M24
M5.4	GHG mitigation guidelines (version 1) Section regarding list of measures	M20 M12 (Sept. 2023)
M5.5	Climate change adaptation guidelines (version 1) Section regarding list of measures	M36 M12 (Sept. 2023)

For any other questions or clarifications, please contact the WP2 team responsible for this guideline.

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13. Proposal for a training module

The table below includes a draft outline for a training module. Training will be planned and organised by WP2, and delivered later this year (2023).

Module 1: Overview
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction 2. The importance of the Climate Farm Demo project 3. The Role of the Climate Farm Advisor
Module 2: Adaptation and Mitigation Measures (AMM's)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adaptation and Mitigation Measures <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. List of AMM's b. Likelihood of implementation c. Impact d. Pre-requisites and systemic barriers e. What supports/ incentives are required (farmer focus)? f. What supports/ incentives are available (researcher/ adviser focus)? 2. Q&A with WP5 about the AMM's
Module 3: GHG Measurement Tools
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Climate Farm Demo GHG measurement tools <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Recommended tools b. Tool selection c. Data collection d. Completing the farm audit e. Reports 4. Competent use of the tool
Module 4: Creating the Adaptation and Mitigation Plan (AMP) and Supporting Its Implementation
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creating the AMP 2. Supporting CFD farmers to reduce GHG emissions 3. Continued support from Climate Farm Demo project

14. Glossary

AMP	Adaptation and Mitigation Plan
AMM	Adaptation and Mitigation Measure
CFD	ClimateFarmDemo (project)
CFA	Climate Farm Advisor
GHG	Greenhouse gases
PDF	Pilot Demo Farmer

15. References

Cawley, A., Heanue, K., Hilliard, R., O'Donoghue, C. and Sheehan, M. (2023), How Knowledge Transfer Impact Happens at the Farm Level: Insights from Advisers and Farmers in the Irish Agricultural Sector, Sustainability, Vol. 15, available online <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/4/3226> , accessed 22/5/23.

Gomes, A and Reidsma, P (2021), Time to Transition: Barriers and Opportunities to Farmer Adoption of Soil GHG Mitigation Practices in Dutch Agriculture, Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems, Vol. 5, available online, <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fsufs.2021.706113/full> , accessed 22/5/23.

Rogers, E. M. (2003), Diffusion of Innovations (5th edition), Free Press, New York.

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